

A case study on Application of Deep learning (ANN) in estimation of WPI

1 Introduction

Water is essential resource for human activities, as well as life. Therefore, water assessment, monitoring and maintenance of it is highly recommended, especially in developing countries. We also consider data classification, modelling, and analytical observations to be essential steps in water quality assessment. Specific approaches are used to assess water quality, out of which one is determining Water Pollution Index (WPI).

Our analysis aims to predict the WPI from important physicochemical parameters of a water sample data set. In order to learn about water quality, we will use one of the Deep Learning techniques, the Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). Moreover, we will use popular Python libraries such as Tensorflow, Keras and Machine Learning techniques such as Adam Optimizer to train the ANN model and predict the WPI .

2 Data

The data contains 14 physicochemical variables characterizing water quality data. These variables are pH, DO, TDS, Alkalinity, EC, Sodium(Na), Calcium(Ca), Magnesium(Mg), Potassium(K), Fluoride(F), Chloride(Cl), Nitrate, Sulphate and Phosphate. WPI is calculated from the selected physicochemical parameter and used as a dependent variable for our analysis.

2.1 Data Preprocessing

Data Normalisation and Standardisation

Artificial Neural Networks are sensitive to the scale of the data. Therefore, we will use MinMax(Normalisation) Scalar from the Scikit learn library to scale the data for estimation of WPI. Normalization is a rescaling of the data from the original range so that all values are within the new range of 0 and 1.

Data Splitting

In order to make sure, we first train the model using only a part of the data and then use the trained model to predict the values for the remaining data that have not been used during the training. Therefore, we split the original data into train and test where 80% of all data fall in the train set, whereas 20% of the data fall in the test set.

3 Methodology

This analysis aims to estimate the water pollution index and water quality class using measured 14 physicochemical parameters. The WPI will serve as the dependent variable, while the other 14

physicochemical parameters are independent. The analysis will help us understand which parameter has the higher impact on affecting the quality of water.

Water pollution index (WPI)

A new comprehensive and flexible index, i.e., water pollution index (WPI) is by Hossain and Patra 2020, that can be applied for physical, chemical (major ions or metal ions) or even for biological quality assessment of water sources based on the available water quality standards for various purposes. WPI can provide direct or overall knowledge of water quality status in the context of any designated use.

For this purpose, 14 water quality parameters are selected to estimate the pollution load of water by applying WPI, based on their standard permissible limits as defined by the BIS (2012) and WHO (2011). However, WPI can accommodate more number variables as it is flexible for n number of parameters. In the first step the pollution load (PLi) of ith parameter was calculated using the following formula

$$PLi = 1 + ((Ci - Si) / Si)$$

where, Ci indicates observed concentration of ith parameter, Si is the standard or highest permissible limit for the respective parameter. Here, the difference between Ci and Si is divided by the respective Si for recognizing the decreased or increased in the standardized value (PLi) of a particular parameter pertaining to its standard permissible limit (Si). In case of pH, a value of 7 is considered as neutral, but < 7 or > 7 are detrimental. With this view following equations are recommended for different pH ranges.

If, the pH is < 7, then below equation is recommended. Where, Sia is minimum acceptable pH value i.e., 6.5

$$PLi = 1 + ((Ci - 7) / (Sia - 7))$$

If, pH is > 7, then Sib would be maximum acceptable pH value i.e., 8.5 and the suggested equation is mentioned below

$$PLi = 1 + ((Ci - 7) / (Sib - 7))$$

Ultimately, the pollution status of a sample or water pollution index (WPI) with n number of variables (parameters) can be evaluated through aggregating the entire pollution load and finally dividing with n, as mentioned in the following formula. In rare cases if measured concentration of a parameter is 0, that should be excluded from total n for that sample.

$$WPI = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n PLi$$

WPI may be considered as an integrated approach as it converts all the input parameters to a single value index to classify the water quality, where any little change in concentration of any input variable can change the WPI class of water quality. Moreover, WPI is free from the use of any theoretical ideal value or dissimilar weights of any variables, which is a practice in some of the conventional indexing approaches. WPI can be applied with a wide range of data sets (i.e. even when the variables are not

normally distributed and skewed). Besides, the use of different indices for different purposes may be lengthy and time-consuming for a single study, where WPI can deliver a general idea of water quality status in context with any input parameters and can be applied for any designated purpose by just applying the standard guideline values for that particular use (Hossain and Patra 2020).

Main Reference:

Hossain M, Patra PK (2020) Water pollution index – a new integrated approach to rank water quality. *Ecol Indic* 117:106668. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106668>

Artificial Neural Networks

Deep Learning has become one of the most popular subfields of Machine Learning. It is a series of algorithms inspired by the structure and function of the brain called Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). Deep Learning allows quantitative models composed of multiple processing layers to study the data representation with multiple levels of abstraction. It has drastically refined state-of-the-art speech recognition, object detection, visual object recognition, and many other disciplines such as drug discovery and genomics.

The entire idea behind Deep Learning is to mimic how human brains work, given that the human brain is one of the most powerful tools for learning. When comparing to the human brain, Neural Networks refer to systems of neurons, either organic or artificial. A neuron is the basic building block of Neural Networks. Figure 1 visualizes the architecture of a neuron. A neuron has a body located in the left lower part of the figure, with such branches emerging from it referred to as Dendrites (the receiver of the signal), and it has an Axon (the transmitters of the signals), which is that long tail connects the neuron's body to the other neurons, which are often referred to as synapses in the Deep Learning terminology.

Figure 1: The Architecture of Neuron

Then the signals are passed to other receptors through these Synapses. Then the cell body sums all those input signals to generate output. The same idea is used in the ANN. Multiple input signals,

referred to as Input Layer Neurons, are transmitted to Hidden Layer Neurons, which on its turn, are used to predict the output, named Output Layer. In this sense, input signals are similar to the human senses, such as human sight, hearing, smelling, tasting and touching, only in the case of ANN, those input signals can be various types of features characterising an observation. This process is visualised by Figure 2, which shows an example of ANN with 3 input signals forming the Input Layer Neurons set, 3 Hidden Layers and 1 Output Layer. Neural networks adapt to changing input so that they can generate the best possible result as required in the output layer.

Figure 2: The Architecture of Neuron

The neural network is often compared to the multiple linear regression, where one uses many input features called independent variables to predict the output variable. The neural network uses Input Layer Neurons to get information and learn about the outcome variable, the Output layer. The main difference between these regression and neural networks is that the former process runs in a single iteration by minimizing the residual sum of squares (just like the cost function), whereas, for neural networks, there is an intermediate step. It is represented by a hidden layer neuron used to acquire a signal from the input layer and learn it multiple times on the observations until the goal is achieved. So it can be said that ANNs are much more sophisticated than multiple linear regression.

Analysis and Results

The physicochemical parameters analyzed are pH, DO, TDS, Alkalinity, EC, Sodium(Na), Calcium(Ca), Magnesium(Mg), Potassium(K), Fluoride(F), Chloride(Cl), Nitrate, Sulphate and Phosphate. The data is divided into two types: a training data set used to develop the models and a validation data set used to validate the models developed using the `train_test_split` function from the `sklearn` library. Then, the criteria performances of the model were evaluated.

Descriptive statistic of data used

	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
pH	485.0	7.808880	0.411552	5.100000	7.550000	7.860000	8.100000	8.570000
DO	485.0	7.436784	1.106868	4.200000	6.700000	7.400000	8.100000	13.500000
TDS	485.0	115.889278	47.332843	56.000000	84.000000	102.000000	129.000000	308.000000
Alkalinity	485.0	62.251546	20.104135	8.000000	50.000000	56.000000	72.000000	170.000000
EC	485.0	196.757361	81.181745	98.000000	140.000000	171.100000	220.000000	502.000000
Na	485.0	8.911093	5.730719	2.190000	5.290000	7.100000	10.240000	48.350000
Ca	485.0	43.756701	17.846411	14.000000	32.000000	40.000000	52.000000	146.000000
Mg	485.0	24.387629	10.829170	2.000000	16.000000	22.000000	28.000000	84.000000
K	485.0	3.042495	2.306840	0.500000	1.770000	2.420000	3.400000	18.020000
F	485.0	0.512101	0.495054	0.059000	0.249000	0.312000	0.466000	3.060000
Cl	485.0	14.180745	9.297846	3.800000	8.600000	11.000000	16.400000	73.300000
Nitrate	485.0	1.291492	1.840738	0.003985	0.246000	0.535983	1.526653	9.716972
Sulphate	485.0	14.829563	14.662305	0.792000	5.544000	9.570000	18.030000	104.480000
Phosphate	485.0	0.089608	0.156697	0.000000	0.023700	0.046252	0.091000	1.765000
WPI	485.0	0.293930	0.132472	0.103531	0.222014	0.254719	0.312652	1.604375

Firstly, a correlation analysis of physicochemical parameters and WPI was carried out to have information about relationships between the parameters.

```

WPI          1.000000
Phosphate    0.873994
EC           0.513956
TDS          0.508326
F            0.478907
Ca           0.462190
Sulphate     0.437575
Na           0.437277
Cl           0.432111
K            0.376962
Nitrate      0.342504
Mg           0.331117
Alkalinity   0.306938
pH           -0.004190
DO           -0.087564
Name: WPI, dtype: float64
    
```


After data processing (Normalisation of data), the ANN models were developed to predict the WPI.

ANN Model Architecture:

Model: "sequential"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
dense (Dense)	(None, 6)	90
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 6)	42
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 1)	7
Total params: 139		
Trainable params: 139		
Non-trainable params: 0		

None

ANN model consists of 14 input parameters viz pH, DO, TDS, Alkalinity, EC, Sodium(Na), Calcium(Ca), Magnesium(Mg), Potassium(K), Fluoride(F), Chloride(Cl), Nitrate, Sulphate and Phosphate and one out parameter/variable i.e., WPI. Here, we are building a neural network which has 14 inputs, two hidden layer of 6neurons each and one output (WPI). The model used is referred as Sequential as the model is created layer-by-layer. The number of parameters for each layer is calculate as : $output_size * (input_size + 1) = number_parameters$. For eg: for layer dense; Param= 6 [output_size]*(14 [input_size]+

1[bias])=90, similarly for dense_1; Param=6*(6+1)=42 and for dense_2-Param=1*(6+1)=7. Hence total no. of parameters= 90+42+7= 139.

Training and Testing ANN Model

For training and evaluation, the original data is split into train and test, where 80% of all data fall in the train set, whereas 20% of the data fall in the test set. The above sequential model is fit into the train set and validated into a test set, and for learning the algorithm, the trained dataset with a batch size of 32 and epochs=500 is used. The batch size=32 signifies that the model will take the first 32 samples (from 1st to 32nd) from the training data set and train the network. Next, it takes the second 32 samples (from 33rd to 65th) and trains the network again. This continues till all the data is introduced into the model. An epoch means training the neural network with all the training data for one cycle. In an epoch, we use all of the data exactly once. An epoch comprises one or more batches, where we use a part of the dataset to train the neural network. Here we have considered epochs=500 and have trained the algorithm with a sample batch size of 32, and when all the data is fed into the algorithm, it completes one epoch. Similarly, the data is provided 500 times in the size of 32 to train the model.

Evaluation

The accuracy of the ANN-based estimation model was evaluated by various criteria including mean squared error (MSE), mean absolute error (MAE), Root-mean squared error (RMSE) and Regression score (R^2).

```
MAE: 0.0011959659993026907
MSE: 1.0561488969213024e-05
RMSE: 0.00324984445307972
Variance Regression Score: 0.9996547699376006
```


The model provides 99.96% accuracy when epochs=500, it was observed that when epochs were reduced the accuracy of the model was showing decreasing trend.

Code:

